

Social Farming for the Elderly

The situation in Ireland

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GLOSSARY

CSO: The Central Statistics Office is the statistical agency responsible for the gathering of information relating to economic, social and general activities and conditions in Ireland, in particular the National Census which is held every five years.

Fair Deal Scheme: – see Nursing home Support Scheme

Farcura: European Union Erasmus+ funded project with partners from Slovenia, Germany, Portugal, Belgium and Ireland. The project created a report, outlined 14 social farming case studies and developed an introductory training course on social farming.

GNI: Stands for Gross National Income or the total amount of money earned by a nation's people and businesses.

IRD Duhallow: A community-based integrated rural development company that was established in 1989. The company combines the efforts and resources of the State Bodies, Local Authorities, Local Communities and individual entrepreneurs for the benefit of the local areas.

Kerry Social Farming: Established in 2013 and operating social farms since 2014, Kerry Social Farming (KSF) was founded on principles of equality, social inclusion, voluntary community development and collaboration. It is currently one of two projects operating the voluntary model of social farming in Ireland, in that farmers are not paid for their time with participants.

Nursing Home Support Scheme: The Nursing Homes Support Scheme, also known as the Fair Deal Scheme, is a scheme of financial support for people who need long-term nursing home care.. Under the Nursing Homes Support Scheme, you will make a contribution towards the cost of your care and the State will pay the balance. This applies whether the nursing home is public, private or voluntary.

Social Farming Ireland: Social Farming Ireland is funded by the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) Social Farming Ireland. It is based in Drumshanbo. Co. Leitrim and is led by Leitrim Development Company. It supports the development of a national Social Farming network in collaboration with other Local Development Companies,

Social Justice Ireland: an independent think tank and justice advocacy organisation that advances the lives of people and communities through providing independent social analysis and effective policy development to create a sustainable future for every member of society and for societies as a whole.

Sofab: Social farming across borders was an EU INTERREG IVA-funded project which operated in the Border counties of Ireland and all of Northern Ireland in the period 2011-2014. It provided funding for and organised social farming placements on family farms, linking local farmers with services in need of activities for their participants.

TILDA: The Irish Longitudinal Study on Ageing is a large-scale, nationally representative, longitudinal study on ageing in Ireland, the overarching aim of which is to make Ireland the best place in the world to grow old.

1 GROWING OLDER IN IRELAND

1.1 Overview of the social system for elderly people

As of the 2016 census, the proportion of Ireland's population over the age of 65 was 19%, which equates to approximately 700,000 people. The state provides for the financial welfare of retired and elderly people principally through a state pension. There are also a number of other allowances available such as a winter fuel allowance, housing allowances, and supports, a living alone allowance, a free travel pass and other allowances and payments based on special circumstances. The current qualifying age for the old-age pension is 66.

The state also provides health care support for elderly people. A means-tested medical card provides holders with full access to medical services and medication. Funding is also available for home care assistance. In cases where long-term residential care is required the state will pay for the care either fully or for people assessed to have sufficient means, through its Nursing Home Support Scheme - also known as the 'Fair Deal Scheme'. For eligible participants, this scheme will pay a portion of the nursing home care and will provide a loan to the client which will pay the balance. The loan is linked to a portion of the individual's assets and is usually repaid through the sale of assets after the client dies.

In addition to these financial and health care supports there are also several social supports and activities available for elderly people. The majority of these are provided by the community and voluntary organisations, local development companies and charities and most receive financial and other support from the state.

1.2 Demographic development

As is the case in most European countries Ireland is facing a situation, over the coming decades, where the proportion of its population who are retired or elderly will increase significantly relative to those of younger and working age. This has led the state to consider how to; on one level address the financial implications of this demographic change and, on another examine what types of activities and care options can be developed to cater for an ageing population.

The Republic of Ireland has a total population of 5.01 million (CSO, 2021). The current demographic structure in Ireland is quite favourable, with approximately 4 workers for every retiree (Department of Finance, 2021). In these calculations, the working-age population consists of those people between the ages of 24 and 64, whilst the old-age population are those of 65 years and older. As of now Ireland's old age dependency ratio allows for a vibrant and robust economy and ensures that, so long as employment levels remain high, the public finances will be relatively stable. While Ireland's old-age dependency ratio is favourable at present and is slightly better than the European average, it is clear that over the coming years it will begin to disimprove considerably.

It is estimated that over the next 3 decades Ireland's ratio of workers to retirees will fall from 4 to just over 2. This will have a considerable impact on the public finances. A smaller working population and a larger dependent cohort will lead to slower revenue growth and rising public expenditure. By 2050,

inflation-adjusted age-related expenditure will be €17 billion per annum more than it is today, rising to €22 billion by 2070. If there were no policy interventions in advance this demographic adjustment would add about 20 percentage points to Ireland's debt to GNI ratio by 2050. In the years after 2050, the fiscal shortfall would worsen significantly so that by 2070 the debt to GNI ratio would reach 180 per cent of GNI. The Department of Finance assesses that revenue increases alone will not be able to fund this growth in expenses – a mix of approaches will be needed. (Department of Finance, 2021).

This arising situation makes it inevitable that there will have to be consequential changes with regard to pensions and elderly health and social welfare provisions. At present, the main thrust of the reforms being considered is on pensions, because this is the most visible and quantifiable element to be impacted by the coming demographic changes. And while fiscal planning is essential to ensuring that ageing and elderly members of society are well provided for there are many other aspects to this story. There will be many elderly people who will be retired and inactive, some will be healthy, some not. Activities and care facilities will need to be developed to cater for their needs in the best possible way.

1.3 Special challenges

Getting a sense of the needs of ageing and elderly people is an essential part of preparation work for the coming challenges of an ageing population. One of the ways in which this is being carried out is through The Irish Longitudinal Study on Ageing, or TILDA for short. This comprehensive study is being run by Trinity College Dublin (TCD) in partnership with a number of other universities and colleges throughout Ireland. The ongoing study has been carried out in five waves of research where interviews have been conducted and questionnaires administered to 8,504 individuals - all over 50 years of age. In addition, the participants, who are all volunteers, agree to periodic health assessments. The research team is composed of an inter-disciplinary panel of experts in various fields of ageing.

The study which began in 2009 looks at the health, lifestyles and financial situation of the participants and how their circumstances change as they grow older over a 10-year period. It also seeks to understand how each of the key components of health, wealth and happiness interact 'such that we can ensure that Ireland meets the needs and choices of its citizens in a personalised and positive environment and with due dignity and respect'. The knowledge gained from the study will form the foundation for economic, health and social policies that benefit all people living in Ireland.

Thus far the study has produced a wide variety of data on factors such as the overall health, quality of life and engagement in a community of older people. It has looked at their involvement with family and whether they support or receive support from their family. It examined the degree to which they utilize health care. The study presents a relatively positive picture of the process of ageing in Ireland, whilst outlining areas of risk related to income in particular. Among its findings is the notion that creative activity levels are high for older people in Ireland and that activities such as hobbies etc. lead to better mental and physical health outcomes.

While TILDA has the worthy ambition of making Ireland the best country in the world to grow old -the current situation for elderly people in Ireland is already challenging. Ireland has one of the lowest life expectancy rates and our older people are amongst the least healthy in Europe. The factors which contribute to this are as yet unknown. The recent report Ageing and Public Health (Sheehan and O Sullivan, 2020) found 'pronounced differences' in health and disability by age group, gender and socio-economic groups in both Ireland and Northern Ireland. It found that socioeconomic status, in

particular, is a major factor in the health outcomes of people aged 65 and older in both countries. In the Republic of Ireland, in 2017, 43% of people over 65s reported a long-term limiting health condition. This compared with just 16% of those in the highest income category.

The report also found that the gap in life expectancy between the most deprived and least deprived areas of Ireland was 5 years less for men and 4.5 years less for females. Differences also exist for gender with females living longer and males enjoying marginally better health outcomes. There are differences too between those over 65s who are professionals and those who are unskilled, with unskilled much more likely to experience health challenges. In the Republic of Ireland, only 27% of professionals have a disability compared to 42% of unskilled workers.

The risk of poverty and deprivation for older people is quite significant. In 2019 it was found that there are 78,000 elderly people or 11.5% of the elderly population living in poverty. A large portion of Ireland's elderly people lives either alone or with another elderly person and these account for 78% of old age poverty. Older people who live on fixed state incomes, without other sources of income are especially vulnerable. (Social Justice Ireland, 2019)

Another key difficulty for elderly people is the issue of mental health. Among the participants of The Irish Longitudinal Study on Ageing (TILDA), it was found that 10% reported clinically significant depressive symptoms and a further 18% reported 'sub-threshold' levels of depression. Anxiety is also common among older adults, with 13% reporting clinically significant symptoms and 29% reporting sub-threshold levels. However, these figures are thought to be much lower than the actual number as many of those with depression and anxiety symptoms do not seek treatment from a medical doctor. Older people also suffer from greater levels of cognitive impairment and memory loss than the general population and these can be contributory factors to poor mental health. It is important to note also that poor mental health is not a normal consequence of ageing and can be "prevented, treated and managed" (Turner et al, 2018).

The issues of loneliness and social isolation are factors that elderly people have to contend with more and more. TILDA reports that almost two-thirds of Irish adults aged 50 and over experienced emotional loneliness at least some of the time. It was found that among TILDA participants those who were 75 years and older were more likely to experience loneliness than younger participants and that lower levels of education were associated with higher levels of loneliness. This held through also for social isolation where those who had completed third-level education were "significantly" less likely to be socially isolated than those who had completed only primary education. Social isolation does not necessarily lead to loneliness or vice versa but it does lead to poorer health and poorer quality of life. The TILDA study found that loneliness and social isolation are not "necessarily a fact of the ageing process" and therefore can be guarded against and addressed (Ward, et. al, 2019).

Elderly people in rural areas

The conditions for people in rural Ireland are often much different from those in cities and towns. There are challenges for rural dwellers around access to services and access to transport. As well as this the impact of rural isolation on mental and physical well-being is well documented. These issues are magnified for older people. Interestingly though in the TILDA study "participants from rural areas (6.5%) were less likely than those from Dublin City or County (10.4%) to be in the most isolated group" (Ward et al. 2019). This indicates that there are more social networks in rural areas, but issues around connectivity are considerably more challenging for rural dwellers without their own transport.

Access to finance is also a major challenge for older people in rural areas. The cost of living for people in rural areas is much higher than for urban dwellers. A 2015 study showed that elderly rural dwellers face an additional €60 per week in expenses compared to their urban counterparts – much of it related to transport. Rural dwellers also have less income than urban dwellers. Earning €102 per week less in 2009 and €134 less in 2012.

Topical to this report is also the number of elderly farmers in rural Ireland. The number of farmers over 65 has been growing steadily over the last couple of decades and is now in the region of 30%. A lot of these farms exist on marginal land where the average output is less than 30,000 euros compared to an average of over 60,000 in areas where the land is of better quality (CSO, 2019). Many of these older farmers are isolated and alone and have therefore an increased risk of mental health challenges.

1.4 Addressing the needs of the elderly

The debate on how to address the challenges of elderly people is not particularly prominent at the present time. It is not part of the public discourse because as mentioned earlier, the demographic profile has not yet reached a point where the issue of ageing is creating strain within society. However taking the Nursing Home Support Scheme/Fair Deal Scheme as an example, there are concerns that the scheme will not be able to keep pace with the rising demand for nursing home places. From a policy perspective, the government is trying to focus on reducing reliance on long-term nursing home care and expanding home care arrangements instead. It is also looking at housing and healthcare initiatives to offer choices other than long-term residential care (Irish Times, 2019).

There is a range of organisations that help address the practical challenges facing the elderly such as health, quality of life and income, some within the auspices of the state, some operating as social enterprises or charities. Some examples of these are:

Age Action

Age Action is a charitable organisation and the leading advocacy group for elderly people in Ireland. Its strategic goals are to:

- Engage stakeholders in the wider community and older people themselves to challenge ageism in laws, policies, systems and communities;
- Guarantee equality and rights for all people as they age;
- Give income security and economic opportunities that uphold older people's dignity and independence;
- Inform and influence policies and practices that give people choice and control over their lives in later life.

Active Retirement Ireland

Active Retirement Ireland (ARI) is a voluntary organisation for older people with a national membership of over 24,500 people and over 550 local associations. The organisation is structured regionally through 9 regions whose role is to bring the local associations together for information, training, seminars and activities. Its focus is to:

- Promote older people as independent, self-organised and active members of their communities;
- Act as a voice for older people and their concerns at the national level;
- Promote positive ageing attitudes in Ireland;
- Provide training, support and information to the local associations of older people in each region;
- Network the local associations for peer support, capacity building and information sharing;

Age and Opportunity

Age & Opportunity is a charitable organisation working to improve the quality of life for people as they age. They develop activity programmes tailored for different settings e.g. the community, the workplace or the care setting and empower volunteers to become activity leaders. Their main priorities are:

- Championing the creativity and value of older people;
- Combating stereotypes and negative views of ageing;
- Developing inclusive and engaging experiences which respond to the interests and needs of the diverse older adult population;
- Developing, testing and measuring the impact of pioneering programmes and approaches;
- Making evidence available to policy-makers and service providers;
- Working with partners and stakeholders to ensure that Ireland's policies, strategies and programmes are directly informed by the needs and experiences of older people.

Friends of the Elderly

Friends of the Elderly Ireland is a non-profit, volunteer-based organisation committed to relieving social isolation and loneliness among the elderly through friendship and companionship. The service pairs its volunteer members with isolated, lonely elderly people allowing companionship and friendships to develop. Its main aims and activities are;

- Provide friendly conversation, companionship and social outings;
- Offer a sense of security knowing that someone will be calling;
- Compliment other available health and social care services;
- Provide a service that is tailored to each individual's needs;

Housing Co-operatives

It is popular in Ireland for community associations and charities to develop housing projects for elderly people. This allows ageing people to retire in an affordable house which they rent from the co-op. They get to live independently in a modern well-insulated house within a community of elderly people where carers are often on hand to meet their basic care needs. These projects are often developed on community land or on land donated by the church.

Other organisation

Along with these organisations, there are also several businesses and charities that provide homecare support and also provide support for disabilities that affect the elderly more than the general population. Of these, the most prominent and well-known is the Alzheimer's Society of Ireland.

Elderly people's contribution to society

It might be said that another key need of the elderly is countering the narrative – popular in public discourse - that older people are dependent and are unable to make a meaningful contribution. Whilst it is true for a portion of the elderly population the idea that all older people are dependent is not borne out by the evidence. In fact, research has found the opposite to be true. Older people are very active in their communities. Over 50% of elderly men and women studied are volunteers, and 72% are members of clubs or groups. Elderly people also regularly provide care or help to relatives, friends or community members – 50% were found to do this in the TILDA study (McGarrigle, et al. 2021).

2 A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO SOCIAL FARMING

2.1 Background

Social farming has become an increasingly popular activity over the last decade. Though no precise definition exists it can be described as the

'short or long-term activities that use agricultural resources such as animals and plants to promote and generate social services in rural areas. Examples of these services include rehabilitation, therapy, sheltered employment, life-long education and other activities that contribute to social inclusion'. (Di Iacovo and O'Connor, 2009)

Although there are many ways in which social farming is practised it typically involves participants spending time on a working farm, contributing to the chores and spending time with the farm owners or staff. The farm is not a therapy centre, it is a working environment but the social farm participants are not there to work per se, (although this may be a beneficial part of their experience) but rather to have an experience as part of their therapy. The mix of experiences that a farm can provide is abundant. Such aspects of farming as the opportunity to work with animals and plants, spend time in nature and socialise with the farm family or the staff of the social farm offer a rich variety of activities and are suitable for a wide range of participants.

In Ireland, social farming has gained significant traction. Up until recently, the practice had been somewhat ad-hoc, but in the wake of the successful Social Farming Across Borders (Sofab) project, it has become more formalised. Sofab was an EU INTERREG IVA-funded project which operated in the Border counties of Ireland and all of Northern Ireland in the period 2011-2014. It provided funding for and organised social farming placements on family farms, linking local farmers with services in need of activities for their participants. This initial idea was then further developed and expanded by Social Farming Ireland, based in Co. Leitrim, to cover the whole country and by Kerry Social Farming in the south-west, with funding sourced through the Department of Agriculture and Food.

2.2 Forms of social farming

There are three different types of social farms found in Ireland.

1. Private - a privately owned family farm that takes on social farming participants for a certain number of hours every week.
2. Third sector - This is where the founding organisation owns and operates the farm.
3. Institutional –where farms are run and/or funded by public bodies.

The way that these farms liaise with service providers and receive funding varies. The three typical approaches are.

1. Farmer model: where the farmer negotiates a contract directly with the Health Service.
2. Placement model: e.g. where a social farming agent or advocate liaises with the host farmer and the service provider to place participants on farms.
3. Organisation model where an organisation or institution uses its own farm to help deliver services. (Crowley, et.al.)

2.3 Social farming providers

Initially, social farming in Ireland was carried out by institutions and then by institutions and the third sector. There are now a growing number of such organisations providing either social farming on farms owned by them or smaller horticultural therapy systems in gardens linked to their premises. These bodies provide services to many different cohorts of participants such as those with mental and/or physical disabilities. It was very rare to find individuals providing social farms and certainly those who were, did it in a very ad hoc manner. However, over the last ten years, the increase in private farms providing social farm placements has been marked.

The growth in the family farm model of social farming has been facilitated by two organisations – *Social Farming Ireland* and *Kerry Social Farming*. These organisations act as catalysts for the activation of social farms. They receive funding from the Department of Agriculture for this work. They link farms with service providers and support individual farmers with training, mentoring, funding and networking etc. You will find further information on these organisations in the *Farcura Social Farming Summary Report* and the *Irish Case Studies* on the Farcura (Farcura.eu) website. Over the last couple of years other Local Development Companies –IRD Duhallow for example- have been successful in sourcing funding for social farming and are currently working on developing programs.

2.4 Target groups

As outlined in the *Farcura State of the art Report on Innovative Farming Methods (2020)* there are four main target groups that social farms cater for in Ireland.

Intellectual Disabilities.

Some of the earliest social farms in Ireland were established to cater for people with intellectual disabilities. In recent years the thrust of government policy has recently moved towards creating activities for people with disabilities that are embedded in the community with a focus on the

principles of 'Person Centeredness, Community Inclusion and Active Citizenship (HSE 2009). This focus is very suitable for social farming activities.

Mental Health

Social farming has become an increasingly popular form of integrative therapy for people suffering from mental health ailments. The family farm model, overseen by Social Farming Ireland, pairs a portion of its farms with local mental health services. The model is very helpful for the re-integration of people who have lost their social network due to short-term or longer-term mental health difficulties. Social Farms help them to re-engage.

Young people, not in education or training.

Social farming provides the opportunity for young people who have become marginalised to engage in meaning full activities and also learn new skills. There is at least one such farm in Ireland the Doon Social Farm run by Ballyhoura Rural Services.

Marginalised groups

Social farms in Ireland also provide places to a range of marginalised groups such as people suffering from addiction to drugs or alcohol or ex-prisoners. They are ideal environments for recovery and re-integration. Other marginalised groups such as asylum seekers have also participated in social farming programs.

3 ELDERLY PEOPLE AS A TARGET GROUP OF SOCIAL FARMING

As Irish society begins to grapple more and more with the challenges of an ageing population. There will be an increasing need to develop policies and innovative solutions to meet the needs of elderly people. From a purely financial perspective, the long-term care model that utilises nursing homes will be difficult to fund as more older people become in need of care. Ways will need to be found to keep people healthier for longer and also provide them with more affordable care when they are no longer able to function as active members of society. In order for this to happen there will need to be developed a mixture of innovative activities and care options to help our ageing population achieve the best quality of life outcomes possible. Social Farming is one activity that can meet many of the challenges and needs identified in this report.

Residential Farms

Developing centres for residential care on farms is increasingly popular in mainland Europe. Whilst not prominent in Ireland, the Camphill communities – one of which is highlighted in our FarmElder case studies – provide us with an example of how a vibrant community can be built around a farm. As mentioned earlier it is common for Irish communities to build co-op housing for their elderly. However, the drawback to these developments is that the elderly are often isolated from other generations, as they are grouped together with other elderly people and rely on artificially created activities. Utilising

this model on working farms would bring added activities, provide active elderly the opportunity to volunteer in the care of animals or crops and the chance for intergenerational mixing.

Elderly Farmers

As outlined earlier the number of elderly farmers has been growing in Ireland. There has also been an increase in farmers experiencing isolation and loneliness. For some of these farmers developing social farming projects on their farms would greatly help alleviate these issues. While not every farmer is suited to social farming there are many who are. Ireland is fortunate to have activator organisations such as Social Farming Ireland, Kerry Social Farming and recently IRD Duhallow, to provide supports to farmers wishing to engage in social farming. This avenue of social farming being a win-win scenario for the elderly host farmer as well as for the participants is ripe for exploitation.

Active Ageing

A key focus of Government policy vis-à-vis the elderly will be to keep people healthy for as long as possible, to reduce the financial burden on the state. As well as this it is the intention of the state to ensure that elderly people have the highest possible quality of life. It is clear from data that these goals are greatly helped when elderly people engage in creative activity. Creative activity has clear “positive associations with health, improved quality of life, reduced loneliness and better mental health” in “community-dwelling adults” over 50. Social farming programmes on farms could be developed as creative activities for elderly people.

Care and Therapy

There is scope for social farming to be utilised as a form of care and or therapy for elderly people. Research has shown how effective social farming is in enhancing the quality of life of participants, providing relief from symptoms of depression and relieving people's experience of social isolation. These are all conditions that characterize the lives of many elderly people. Farm environments also offer the potential to be sites for care homes or treatment centres for people with dementia. There have been many studies showing how horticulture therapy, plants and animals provide relief for people with dementia. Many dementia treatment centres construct gardens so that they can introduce horticultural programs. Farms with their ready-made natural environment could be excellent locations for dementia treatments.

4 CURRENT SITUATION OF SOCIAL FARMING FOR ELDERLY PEOPLE IN IRELAND

As can be seen from section 2 the practice of social farming is well developed in Ireland. There are many different types of farming models in operation ranging from institutional farms to small family farms. At this point in its development, however, social farming is not widely used for elderly people. In the case studies associated with this report we have shown some examples of early stage development of social farming projects and also pointed to how a residential social farming model could be adapted to cater for elderly people.

5 CONCLUSION

Ireland is at the beginning of a period of demographic change. Over the coming decades, the share of elderly people per head of population will increase greatly. This report has outlined the main challenges that this will cause for the state as well as the main challenges faced by elderly people. In order to meet these, we will need to develop new ways of delivering services for elderly people. We will also need to adjust our attitude towards the elderly, to cease seeing them as a burden and instead acknowledge their significant contribution to society. It is important that we do not look at all elderly people as a challenge to be managed but find ways to harness the skills, knowledge and wisdom that they can bring to society, both for their own benefit but also for the benefit of society as a whole.

Social farming can play an important role in providing vibrant activities for elderly people to utilise their skills. It can also facilitate care and therapy for elderly people. In some cases social farms could become sites for residential developments for elderly people allowing them the opportunity for intergenerational mixing and to live out their years in a vibrant, working family farm environment. Social farming offers a tremendous amount of potential to address many of the needs of our ageing population

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